

Perception of health and weight

Veillez remplir le questionnaire ci-dessous.

Merci !

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- 1) Given your age and height, you would rather say you are
- Much too skinny
 - A little too skinny
 - About the right weight
 - A little too big
 - Much too big
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- 2) Would you rather say you health is
- Excellent
 - Good
 - Average
 - Bad
 - Very bad